

Short name	Interaction with other decarbonisation technologies	Long name	Interaction with other decarbonisation and low-carbon technologies
Geographical scope	All regions		
Description of how this issue tends to manifest (include footnotes for key references)	<p>Development of CCUS clusters will not happen in a vacuum: at the same time as major CCUS capital and infrastructure projects, similarly large net zero-aligned project such as renewable energy, hydrogen infrastructure and oil and gas decommissioning will also be developed. These projects are likely to be in competition for resources, funding and skilled workers, so long-term strategic planning is needed to ensure that all the activity that needs to happen to reach net zero is able to be done.</p> <p>This includes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Developing fabrication capacity, including fabrication yards and skilled workers • Ensuring there is sufficient clean energy to run processes (particularly CO₂ utilisation) • Understanding the timing and sequencing of big projects • Where workers are expected to re-train and/or move sector, enabling a just transition. <p>CCUS hubs and clusters can be initiated by a variety of different types of actors, such as state entities, trade or dedicated local industry associations, group of major emitters, or oil and gas operators. The important thing is to have or gain the trust of the other parties in order to build momentum and bring everyone on board in a mutually beneficial and transparent manner. Stakeholders have highlighted the need for a framework that allows cooperation rather than promoting competition for funding: for example, the UK Government Cluster Sequencing Competition has selected the first two clusters to be developed in the UK, both in the north of England. While two clusters will received capital support from the CCS Infrastructure Fund and revenue support through the business models which are being developed, clusters and projects which were not selected are understood not to be eligible to access the revenue subsidies provided by the business models, even if they were able to raise the necessary capital to build their projects.</p> <p>Related to this is a need for an industrial vision for carbon neutrality, particularly within clusters. By working together towards the goal of net zero, industries can benefit from economies of scale and provide reassurance to their supply chain about the ongoing need for products, services and workers. Industries in a cluster that do not have a decarbonisation goal may find it hard to make the case to participate. There are tensions to be addressed between having enough transparency to effectively work together, realise cost-efficiency and avoid monopolies and windfall profits; and protecting competition and trade secrets.</p>		

<p>Key examples where this issue manifests (also based on stakeholder inputs)</p>	<p>In the UK, industrial clusters have been funded to develop roadmaps for their transition to net zero: the Scottish Net Zero Roadmap¹, Humber Industrial Cluster Plan², South Wales Industrial Cluster³, Net Zero North West Cluster Plan⁴, Repowering the Black Country⁵ and Net Zero Tees Valley Cluster Plan⁶.</p> <p>In the UK the CCSA and Nuclear AMRC published a <i>CCUS Supply Chain Intervention Strategy</i>⁷. Key recommendations were:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Develop a schedule of key components • Launch a supplier development programme • Increase competitiveness with improved and new production processes • Execute a CCUS-wide supply chain analysis programme <p>In order to avoid conflicts and bottlenecks, this work should extend to all decarbonization and low-carbon infrastructure.</p> <p>The Scottish Government has established a Just Transition Commission⁸, initially to advise Scottish Ministers on how to apply just transition principles⁹, and subsequently to provide scrutiny and advice on Scottish Government-led sectoral just transition plans¹⁰.</p> <p>Stakeholders who responded to the survey additionally highlighted the need to understand the lifecycle cost of renewable energy</p>
<p>Other issues this affects</p>	<p>Complexity of the CCUS value chain</p>

¹ <https://snzr.co.uk>

² <https://www.humberindustrialclusterplan.org/>

³ <https://www.swic.cymru/>

⁴ <https://netzeronw.co.uk>

⁵ <https://www.blackcountrylep.co.uk/our-strategy/place/repowering-the-black-country/>

⁶ <https://www.ukri.org/about-us/how-we-are-doing/research-outcomes-and-impact/innovate-uk/net-zero-tees-valley/>

⁷ <https://namrc.co.uk/wp-content/uploads/2022/03/CCUS-supply-chain-intervention-strategy.pdf>

⁸ <https://www.gov.scot/groups/just-transition-commission/>

⁹ Summarised as: Plan, invest and implement a transition to environmentally and socially sustainable jobs, sectors and economies, building on Scotland's economic and workforce strengths and potential; Create opportunities to develop resource efficient and sustainable economic approaches, which help address inequality and poverty; and Design and deliver low carbon investment and infrastructure, and make all possible efforts to create decent, fair and high value work, in a way which does not negatively affect the current workforce and overall economy.

¹⁰ Just Transition Commission reports include: *Interim Report* (2020)

<https://www.webarchive.org.uk/wayback/archive/20210529112742/https://www.gov.scot/publications/transition-commission-interim-report/>; *Advice for a Green Recovery* (2020)

<https://www.webarchive.org.uk/wayback/archive/20200730180449/https://www.gov.scot/publications/transition-commission-advice-green-recovery/>; *A National Mission for a fairer, greener Scotland* (2021)

<https://www.gov.scot/publications/transition-commission-national-mission-fairer-greener-scotland/>; *Making the Future – second Just Transition Commission: initial report* (2022)

<https://www.gov.scot/publications/making-future-initial-report-2nd-transition-commission/>.

References

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- Net Zero North West; <https://netzeronw.co.uk>, United Kingdom.
- Black Country Local Enterprise Partnership; Repowering the Black Country, <https://www.blackcountrylep.co.uk/our-strategy/place/repowering-the-black-country/>, United Kingdom.
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